

SYNTHESIS OF COMPOUNDS ALLIED TO CHLOROMYCETIN

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The *m*-nitro and *p*-chloro analogues of chloromycetin have been synthesised.

Recently Buu-Hoi *et al.* (*Compt. rend.*, 1950, 230, 662; 229, 1343; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2766) have described the preparation of *m*-nitro and *p*-chloro analogues of chloroamphenicol. We were also working in this direction and in view of the above publications, we are placing on record the results of our observations on the preparation of the above analogues. The scheme of synthesis followed is based on the method of Long and Troutman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2469).

• E X P E R I M E N T A L

p-Chloro Analogue of Chloromycetin

Hexamethylenetetramine Salt of p-Chloro-*o*-bromoacetophenone.—To a mixture of 10.4 g. (0.07 mole) of powdered hexamethylenetetramine and 60 c.c. of dry chloroform after few minutes' stirring at room temperature, was added a solution of *p*-chloro-*o*-bromoacetophenone (15 g., 0.068 mole) in 60 c.c. of chloroform. The temperature of the reaction mixture rose to 48°-50°, which was maintained by external heating for 4 hours. The mixture was cooled to 30° and filtered. The filtered solid was purified by repeated washing with 95% alcohol and filtration, m. p. 162-64°, yield 17 g. (72%). (Found: N, 15.48. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{12}ON_4ClBr$: N, 16.0 per cent).

p-Chloro- α -aminoacetophenone Hydrochloride.—To a stirred solution of 95% alcohol (55 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (27 c.c.) was added hexamethylenetetramine salt (15 g.) and the stirring continued for 16 hours at room temperature (25°). The mixture was cooled to 5° and filtered. The white crystalline product which consisted of the amine hydrochloride and ammonium chloride was stirred for 15 minutes with 12 c.c. of water at 25° and then cooled to 10° and filtered. The dried product weighed 10 g., m.p. 252° (decomp.). (Found: N, 12.96. Calc. for $C_8H_8ONCl.HCl$: N, 13.3 per cent).

p-Chloro- α -acetamidoacetophenone.—To a stirred mixture of *p*-chloro- α -aminoacetophenone (9 g., 0.042 mole), water (30 c.c.) and chipped ice (60 g.) was first added 10 c.c. of acetic anhydride and then rapidly a solution of sodium acetate (13 g.) in 50 c.c. of water. Throughout the operation temperature was kept below 10°. Stirring was continued until temperature rose to 20°, when the reaction mixture was made strongly acid with hydrochloric acid and filtered. The solid product was washed and dried and crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 165-66°, yield 10 g. (98%). (Found: N, 6.30. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{10}O_2NCl$: N, 6.62 per cent).

p-Chloro- α -acetamido- β -hydroxypropioiophenone.—To *p*-chloro- α -acetamidoacetophenone (16 g.) were at first added 95% alcohol (30 c.c.) and 36-38% formaldehyde (7 c.c.) and then sodium bicarbonate (0.4 g.) with stirring and the mixture was stirred for 2 hours at 35° when a clear solution resulted. It was then poured on 400 g. of crushed ice and allowed to stand in the cold when a white powder settled at the bottom, which was collected on a filter paper, yield 15 g. A portion of it on crystallisation from water melted at 119-21°. (Found: N, 5.46. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{12}O_3NCl$: N, 5.79 per cent).

1-p-Chlorophenyl-2-acetamido-1:3-propanediol.—A mixture of *p*-chloro- α -acetamido- β -hydroxypropiofenone (7 g., 0.03 mole), aluminium isopropoxide (11 g., 0.052 mole) and 100 c.c. of dry isopropyl alcohol was slowly distilled from a flask fitted with a stirrer and a Hahn condenser until the distillate showed negative test for acetone (5 hours). Further quantity of isopropyl alcohol was distilled until a total of 60 c.c. was removed. The reaction product was cooled just below reflux temperature and then treated with 10 c.c. of water and the mixture was filtered hot after refluxing for 15 minutes. The filtered solid was twice extracted with 50 c.c. portions of boiling isopropyl alcohol and filtered. The combined filtrate was concentrated *in vacuo* and the oily residue crystallised from ethyl acetate, m. p. 160-62°, yield 3 g. (Found : N, 5.31. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{14}O_2NCl$: N, 5.73 per cent).

1-p-Chlorophenyl-2-amino-1:3-propanediol.—A mixture of the monoacetyl derivative (2.54 g.) and 5% hydrochloric acid (25.4 c.c.) was heated on a steam-bath with occasional swirling. A clear solution resulted within a few minutes and the heating was continued for 1 hour. The solution was cooled slightly, mixed with charcoal and filtered. The yellow solution was cooled and made strongly basic with 20% sodium hydroxide solution. On cooling an almost colorless solid precipitated which was crystallised from water, m. p. 120-21°, yield 1.9 g. (Found : N, 6.46. Calc. for $C_9H_{12}O_2NCl$: N, 6.9 per cent).

m-Nitro Analogue of Chloromycetin

The *m*-nitro analogue of chloromycetin was also prepared by following the above method.

Hexamethylenetetramine salt of *m*-nitro-*o*-bromoacetophenone was obtained by condensing *m*-nitro-*o*-bromoacetophenone (22 g.) with powdered hexamethylenetetramine (14 g.), m. p. 170-72° (decomp.), yield 32 g. (Found ; N, 19.03. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{18}O_2N_3Br$: N, 19.44 per cent).

***m*-Nitro- α -aminoacetophenone hydrochloride** was obtained by converting hexamethylenetetramine salt (30 g.) into amine hydrochloride, m. p. 237-39°, yield 16 g. (Found : N, 12.67. Calc. for $C_8H_8(O_2N_2) \cdot HCl$: N, 12.9 per cent).

***m*-Nitro- α -acetamidoacetophenone** was prepared from *m*-nitro- α -aminoacetophenone hydrochloride (15 g.) with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, yield 9 g. (60%). It was crystallised as yellow needles from ethyl acetate, m. p. 140-43°. (Found : N, 12.36. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_2$: N, 12.61 per cent).

***m*-Nitro- α -acetamido- β -hydroxypropiofenone** was obtained from *m*-nitro- α -acetamidoacetophenone (8 g.) and 35% formaldehyde and sodium bicarbonate, yield 7.2 g. (80%). It was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m. p., 160-62°. (Found : N, 10.9. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{12}O_5N_2$: N, 11.11 per cent).

1 *m*-Nitrophenyl-2-acetamido-1:3-propanediol was obtained on reduction of *m*-nitro- α -acetamido- β -hydroxypropiofenone (7 g.) with aluminium isopropoxide, yield 3.0 g., m. p. 171°. (Found : N, 11.46. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{14}O_5N_2$: N, 11.02 per cent).

1 *m*-Nitro-2-amino-1:3-propanediol was obtained by hydrolysing the monoacetyl derivative (2.5 g., 0.01 mole) with 5% hydrochloric acid at 95° for 2 hours, m. p. 127-29°, yield 1.7 g. (85%). (Found : N, 13.12. Calc. for $C_8H_{12}O_4N_2$: N, 13.4 per cent).